

Project ‘The Third Way’
Prepositional Adverbials from Latin to Romance¹

Statistics for field-based linguistics: processing variation.
Test data on Irpinian (Montella, Southern Italy)
[Annexe]

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Introduction

This project material is to be read as an annexe to a book chapter:

Wissner, Inka / Roy, Alan (in progress): “Statistics for field-based linguistics: processing variation”, in: Hummel *et al.* (edd), *Adverbials with preposition and adjective in Romance: field studies in present-day varieties of French, Italian, Portuguese, Romanian and Spanish*, for De Gruyter, 34 pages.

It provides detailed tables and graphs illustrating the procedure developed for data gathering and processing within the *Third Way* project on prepositional adverbials from Latin to Romance, a project led by Martin Hummel at the University of Graz (Austria) (<https://adjective-adverb.uni-graz.at>), financed by the Austrian Science Fund nr. P 30751-G30, 2018-2022. It has been tested with forms chosen randomly from data retrieved by team members Stefan Koch and Cesarina Vecchia in the Irpinian dialect in Campania, in the South of Italy (Montella): *a bbacando* ‘in vain’, *pe ccerto* ‘for sure’, and *a llieggio* ‘empty, empty-handed, without loading, not stuffed’, respectively numbered 27, 5 and 13 according to Wissner (in progress). It completes

- 1) An online template with empty tables for the fieldworkers to fill in their proper data (Wissner/Roy 2021)
- 2) An online questionnaire model presenting a guide, a questionnaire template and a series of worksheets used for the enquiries (Wissner / Porcel Bueno / Koch / Hummel 2020)
- 3) A journal article presenting the sociolinguistic method developed for the realisation of enquiries in the field, including speaker sampling and cell constitution (Wissner forthcoming)
- 4) A book presenting major results for each analysed dialect (Hummel/Koch/Porcel Bueno/Wissner in progress), including the way the linguistic data is processed (Wissner in progress).

In this annexe, tables present the enquired speakers in terms of numbers (according to their moment of enquiry). They contain the following abbreviations:

- A, B, C: number of the blocs in which a series of questions is asked on each adverbial during the interviews, followed by a number indicating the question, as presented by Wissner / Porcel Bueno / Koch / Hummel (2020, 26; 32-71) and Wissner (in progress):
 - Three questions under bloc A on the adverbials’ recognition (A.1, A.2, A.3) (§ 2.1),
 - Four questions under bloc B on their variational features (B.1, B.2, B.3, B.4) (§ 2.2)
 - Two questions under bloc C on their morphosyntactic variation (answers restructured, C.1, C.2) (§ 2.3),
- CI: Confidence interval (§ 2.1-2.4): see Wissner/Roy in progress
- F: female speaker
- M: male speaker
- NA: not applicable
- p = P-value (on the standard scale of 0-1)
- sign: significant

Qualitative answers of each informant (yes/no/not sure; free answers) are translated into quantitative answers; first, they are reported as simple numbers into the tables (e.g.: p. 7, A.1: ‘No’: 0; ‘Yes’: 23, that is: 23 informants corresponded ‘Yes’); second, the probability of obtaining the same result if the test was to be reproduced is measured with a simulated value on a common scale of 10 with uncertainties, calculated considering statistical fluctuation as argued in Wissner/Roy (in progress). The significance of the values’ group-dependency is here presented in terms of probabilities estimated with Roy’s calculator (2021-2022) by the means of hypothesis testing which integrates the Student’s-*t*-test with Welch’s unequal variance *t*-test extension; these results are compared to results based on a standardised Fisher-Freemann-Halton test in case of significant differences (Lowry 1998-2023), as detailed in Wissner/Roy (in progress).

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1. Aggregating and correlating data retrieved in qualitative fieldwork

I Meta data with values	Gender	Age	A.1	A.2	B.1	B.2	B.3	B.4	C.1	C.2	A.1	A.2	B.1	B.2	B.3	B.4	C1	C2	A.1	A.2	B.1	B.2	B.3	B.4	C1	C2
			Recog- nition (0-10)	Local recog- nition (0-10)	Fre- quency (1-7.5- 10)	Age- distribu- tion (1-5.5- 10)	Infor- mal- ity (1- 5.5- 10)	Ora- lity (1-5.5- 10)	Vari- ation 1 (0-10)	Vari- ation 2 (0-10)	27: a bbac- ando	27	27	27	27	27	27	27	27	27	13: a llieg- gio	13	13	13	13	13
Scale Item / Speak- er nr.	N	r	5: pe ccerto	5 (cf. re cierto)	5	5	5	5	5	5	27: a bbac- ando	27	27	27	27	27	27	27	13: a llieg- gio	13	13	13	13	13	13	13
1	m	57	10	10	7.5	10	5.5	10	0	10	10	10	7.5	10	5.5	10	0	0	10	10	7.5	10	5.5	10	10	0
2	m	76	10	10	1	10	5.5	10	0	0	10	10	1	10	5.5	10	0	0	10	10	1	10	5.5	10	10	0
3	f	69	10	10	1	10	5.5	10	0	0	10	10	1	10	5.5	10	0	0	10	10	1	10	5.5	10	10	0
4	m	75	10	10	1	10	5.5	5.5	0	0	10	10	10	5.5	5.5	10	0	0	10	10	1	10	5.5	10	10	0
5	f	61	10	10	1	10	5.5	10	0	0	10	10	10	5.5	5.5	5.5	0	0	10	10	1	10	5.5	10	10	0
6	f	38	10	0	0 (NS)	0 (NS)	0 (NS)	0 (NS)	0 (NS)	0 (NS)	10	10	10	5.5	5.5	10	0	0	0	0	NA	N A	N A	N A	10	0
7	f	34	10	0	0 (NS)	0 (NS)	0 (NS)	0 (NS)	0 (NS)	0 (NS)	10	10	10	5.5	5.5	10	0	0	0	0	NA	N A	N A	N A	10	0
8	f	60	10	10	10	5.5	5.5	10	0	10	10	10	7.5	10	5.5	10	0	0	10	10	1	5.5	5.5	5.5	10	10
9	f	46	10	10	10	5.5	5.5	10	0	10	10	10	7.5	10	5.5	10	0	0	10	10	1	5.5	5.5	5.5	10	10
10	m	25	10	10	7.5	10	5.5	10	10	10	10	10	7.5	5.5	5.5	5.5	0	0	0	0	NA	N A	N A	N A	10	10
11	m	26	10	10	7.5	10	5.5	10	10	10	10	10	7.5	5.5	5.5	5.5	0	0	0	0	NA	N A	N A	N A	10	10
12	m	74	10	10	7.5	10	5.5	10	0	10	10	10	1	10	5.5	10	0	0	10	10	1	10	5.5	10	10	0
13	f	62	10	10	7.5	10	5.5	10	0	0	10	10	1	10	5.5	10	0	0	10	10	1	10	5.5	10	10	0
14	f	48	10	10	1	10	5.5	10	0	0	10	10	7.5	10	5.5	10	0	0	10	10	7.5	10	5.5	10	0	10
15	m	57	10	10	1	10	5.5	10	10	10	10	10	7.5	10	5.5	10	0	0	10	10	7.5	10	5.5	10	10	0
16	m	33	10	10	7.5	10	5.5	5.5	0	0	10	10	10	10	5.5	5.5	0	0	0	0	NA	N A	N A	N A	10	0
17	f	33	10	10	7.5	10	5.5	5.5	0	0	10	10	10	10	5.5	5.5	0	10	10	10	1	10	5.5	10	0	0
18	m	29	10	10	10	5.5	5.5	5.5	0	10	10	10	10	5.5	5.5	5.5	0	0	10	10	1	5.5	5.5	10	10	0
19	m	27	10	10	10	5.5	5.5	5.5	0	10	10	10	10	5.5	5.5	10	0	0	0	0	NA	N A	N A	N A	10	10
22	f	73	10	10	7.5	5.5	5.5	10	0	10	10	10	1	10	5.5	10	0	0	10	10	1	10	5.5	10	10	0
23	f	51	10	10	7.5	5.5	5.5	10	10	10	10	10	1	10	5.5	10	0	0	0	0	NA	N A	N A	N A	0	0
24	f	31	10	10	10	5.5	5.5	5.5	0	10	10	10	10	5.5	5.5	5.5	0	0	10	10	1	10	5.5	10	10	10
25	f	28	10	10	10	5.5	5.5	5.5	0	10	10	10	10	5.5	5.5	5.5	0	0	10	10	1	10	5.5	10	10	10

Table 1: Raw data for each individual speaker in the Italian population and each question, juxtaposed to synthesised metadata

I Meta data with values	Gender	Age	A.1	B.1	B.2	B.3	B.4	C.1	A.1	B.1	B.2	B.3	B.4	C.1	A.1	B.1	B.2	B.3	B.4	C.1
			Recognition A.2 if different (0-10)	Fre- quency (1-7.5- 10)	Age- distribu- tion (1-5.5- 10)	Infor- mality (1-5.5- 10)	Ora- lity (1-5.5- 10)	C.2 Variation (0-10)	/ A.2 if different						C.2	/ A.2 if differ- ent				
Scale Item / Speak- er nr.	N r □	→	5: <i>pe- ccerto cf. re certo</i>	5	5	5	5	5	27: <i>a- bbacando</i>	27	27	27	27	27	13: <i>a- llieggio</i>	13	13	13	13	13
Y o n g e r			speakers																	
10	m	25	10	7.5	10	5.5	10	10 10	10	7.5	5.5	5.5	5.5	0 0	0	NA	NA	NA	NA	10 10
11	m	26	10	7.5	10	5.5	10	10 10	10	7.5	5.5	5.5	5.5	0 0	0	NA	NA	NA	NA	10 10
19	m	27	10	10	5.5	5.5	5.5	0 10	10	10	5.5	5.5	10	0 0	0	NA	NA	NA	NA	10 10
25	f	28	10	10	5.5	5.5	5.5	0 10	10	10	5.5	5.5	5.5	0 0	10	1	10	5.5	10	10 10
18	m	29	10	10	5.5	5.5	5.5	0 10	10	10	5.5	5.5	5.5	0 0	10	1	5.5	5.5	10	10 0
2 nd Sub-			group																	
24	f	31	10	10	5.5	5.5	5.5	0 10	10	10	5.5	5.5	5.5	0 0	10	1	10	5.5	10	10 10
16	m	33	10	7.5	10	5.5	5.5	0 0	10	10	10	5.5	5.5	0 0	0	NA	NA	NA	NA	10 0
17	f	33	10	7.5	10	5.5	5.5	0 0	10	10	10	5.5	5.5	0 10	10	1	10	5.5	10	0 0
7	f	34	10 0	0 (NS)	0 (NS)	0 (NS)	0 (NS)	0 (NS)	10	10	5.5	5.5	10	0 0	0	NA	NA	NA	NA	10 0
6	f	38	10 0	0 (NS)	0 (NS)	0 (NS)	0 (NS)	0 (NS)	10	10	5.5	5.5	10	0 0	0	NA	NA	NA	NA	10 0
E l d e r l y			speakers																	
9	f	46	10	10	5.5	5.5	10	0 10	10	7.5	10	5.5	10	0 0	10	1	5.5	5.5	5.5	10 10
14	f	48	10	1	10	5.5	10	0 0	10	7.5	10	5.5	10	0 0	10	7.5	10	5.5	10	0 10
23	f	51	10	7.5	5.5	5.5	10	10 10	10	1	10	5.5	10	0 0	0	NA	NA	NA	NA	0 0
1	m	57	10	7.5	10	5.5	10	0 10	10	7.5	10	5.5	10	0 0	10	7.5	10	5.5	10	10 0
15	m	57	10	1	10	5.5	10	10 10	10	7.5	10	5.5	10	0 0	10	7.5	10	5.5	10	10 0
8	f	60	10	10	5.5	5.5	10	0 10	10	7.5	10	5.5	10	0 0	10	1	5.5	5.5	5.5	10 10
5	f	61	10	1	10	5.5	10	0 0	10	10	5.5	5.5	5.5	0 0	10	1	10	5.5	10	10 0
13	f	62	10	7.5	10	5.5	10	0 0	10	1	10	5.5	10	0 0	10	1	10	5.5	10	10 0
2 nd Sub-			group																	
3	f	69	10	1	10	5.5	10	0 0	10	1	10	5.5	10	0 0	10	1	10	5.5	10	10 0
22	f	73	10	7.5	5.5	5.5	10	0 10	10	1	10	5.5	10	0 0	10	1	10	5.5	10	10 0
12	m	74	10	7.5	10	5.5	10	0 10	10	1	10	5.5	10	0 0	10	1	10	5.5	10	10 0
4	m	75	10	1	10	5.5	5.5	0 0	10	10	5.5	5.5	10	0 0	10	1	10	5.5	10	10 0
2	m	76	10	1	10	5.5	10	0 0	10	1	10	5.5	10	0 0	10	1	10	5.5	10	10 0

Table 2: Raw data for each individual speaker categorised in two age groups in the Italian population and each question, juxtaposed to synthesised metadata

I Meta data with values	Gender	Age	A.1 Recogni- tion A.2 if different (0-10)	B.1 Fre- quency (1-7.5- 10)	B.2 Age- distribu- tion (1-5.5- 10)	B.3 Forma- lity (1-5.5- 10)	B.4 Ora- lity (1-5.5- 10)	C.1 C.2 Varia- tion (0-10)	A.1 A.2	B.1	B.2	B.3	B.4	C.1 C.2	A.1 A.2	B.1	B.2	B.3	B.4	C.1 C.2
			Scale Item / Speak- er nr.	N r □	→ →	5: pe- ccerto cf. re certo	5	5	5	5	5	27: a bbacando	27	27	27	27	27	13: a lleggio	13	13
Male			speakers																	
1	m	57	10	7.5	10	5.5	10	0 10	10	7.5	10	5.5	10	0 0	10	7.5	10	5.5	10	10 0
2	m	76	10	1	10	5.5	10	0 0	10	1	10	5.5	10	0 0	10	1	10	5.5	10	10 0
4	m	75	10	1	10	5.5	5.5	0 0	10	10	5.5	5.5	10	0 0	10	1	10	5.5	10	10 0
10	m	25	10	7.5	10	5.5	10	10 10	10	7.5	5.5	5.5	5.5	0 0	0	NA	NA	NA	NA	10 10
11	m	26	10	7.5	10	5.5	10	10 10	10	7.5	5.5	5.5	5.5	0 0	0	NA	NA	NA	NA	10 10
12	m	74	10	7.5	10	5.5	10	0 10	10	1	10	5.5	10	0 0	10	1	10	5.5	10	10 0
15	m	57	10	1	10	5.5	10	10 10	10	7.5	10	5.5	10	0 0	10	7.5	10	5.5	10	10 0
16	m	33	10	7.5	10	5.5	5.5	0 0	10	10	10	5.5	5.5	0 0	0	NA	NA	NA	NA	10 0
18	m	29	10	10	10	5.5	5.5	0 10	10	10	5.5	5.5	5.5	0 0	10	1	5.5	5.5	10	10 0
19	m	27	10	10	10	5.5	5.5	0 10	10	10	5.5	5.5	10	0 0	0	NA	NA	NA	NA	10 10
Female			speakers																	
3	f	69	10	1	10	5.5	10	0 0	10	1	10	5.5	10	0 0	10	1	10	5.5	10	10 0
5	f	61	10	1	10	5.5	10	0 0	10	10	5.5	5.5	5.5	0 0	10	1	10	5.5	10	10 0
6	f	38	10 0	0 (NS)	0 (NS)	0 (NS)	0 (NS)	0 (NS)	10	10	5.5	5.5	10	0 0	0	NA	NA	NA	NA	10 0
7	f	34	10 0	0 (NS)	0 (NS)	0 (NS)	0 (NS)	0 (NS)	10	10	5.5	5.5	10	0 0	0	NA	NA	NA	NA	10 0
8	f	60	10	10	5.5	5.5	10	0 10	10	7.5	10	5.5	10	0 0	10	1	5.5	5.5	5.5	10 10
9	f	46	10	10	5.5	5.5	10	0 10	10	7.5	10	5.5	10	0 0	10	1	5.5	5.5	5.5	10 10
13	f	62	10	7.5	10	5.5	10	0 0	10	1	10	5.5	10	0 0	10	1	10	5.5	10	10 0
14	f	48	10	1	10	5.5	10	0 0	10	7.5	10	5.5	10	0 0	10	7.5	10	5.5	10	0 10
17	f	33	10	7.5	10	5.5	5.5	0 0	10	10	10	5.5	5.5	0 10	10	1	10	5.5	10	0 0
22	f	73	10	7.5	5.5	5.5	10	0 10	10	1	10	5.5	10	0 0	10	1	10	5.5	10	10 0
23	f	51	10	7.5	5.5	5.5	10	10 10	10	1	10	5.5	10	0 0	0	NA	NA	NA	NA	0 0
24	f	31	10	10	5.5	5.5	5.5	0 10	10	10	5.5	5.5	5.5	0 0	10	1	10	5.5	10	10 10
25	f	28	10	10	5.5	5.5	5.5	0 10	10	10	5.5	5.5	5.5	0 0	10	1	10	5.5	10	10 10

Table 3: Raw data for individuals presented in two subgroups according to gender in the Italian population and each question, juxtaposed to synthesised metadata

2. Analysing fieldwork data to identify the prepositional adverbials' usage

2.1. Do speakers know the tested prepositional adverbials?

Questions	A.1 Have you already heard this expression? Possible answers: Yes – No – Not sure.					A.2 ... here in the area? Possible answers: Yes – No – Not sure.					
	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2	
A.1-A.2 Recognition	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2	
Categories exclusive Answers in absolute numbers and %	Threshold for unknown	0. No / Not sure	10. Yes	I.a Value with uncertainties on a scale of 0 to 10	I.a Signifi- cance (p)**	Threshold for unknown	0. No / Not sure	10. Yes	II.a Value with uncertainties (scale 0-10)	II.b Signifi- cance (p)**	
Ital. [Montella] <i>pe ccerto</i>	0.4	0	23 (100 %)	9.7 +0.3 / -1.8 [83 % CI: +0.2/ -1.6]		0.4	2	21 (91 %)	8.9 +1.0 / -2.1 [83 % CI: +0.9 / -1.9]		
Male speakers	1.0	0	10 (100 %)	9.4 +0.6 / -3.5 [83 % CI: +0.5 / -3.0]	$p =$ 0.91	1.0	0	10 (100 %)	9.4 +0.6 / -3.5 [83 % CI: +0.5 / -3.0]	$p =$ 0.41	
Female speakers	0.8	0	13 (100 %)	9.5 +0.5 / -2.9 [83 % CI: +0.4 / -2.5]	not sign. At all	0.8	2	11 (91%)	8.1 +1.7/ -3.2 [83 % CI: +1.4 / -2.8]	not sign. At all	
Younger speakers	1.0	0	10 (100 %)	9.4 +0.6 / -3.5 [83 % CI: +0.5 / -3.0]	$p =$ 0.91	1.0	2	8 (80 %)	7.6 +2.1 / -3.7 [83 % CI: +1.8 / -3.2]	$p =$ 0	
Elder speakers	0.8	0	13 (100 %)	9.5 +0.5 / -2.9 [83 % CI: +0.4 / -2.5]	not sign. At all	0.8	0	11 (91%)	9.5 +0.5 / 2.9 [83 % CI: +0.4 / -2.5]	not sign.	
4 age-groups	A.1					A.2					p=*
Speakers aged 18 to 29						2.0	0	5	8.9 +1.1 / - 5.3 [83% CI: +0.9 / -4.4]	$p =$ 0.65	
Speakers aged 30-45		$p = 0.16$	$p = 0.83$	$p = 1.0$		2.0	2	3	5.8 +3.7 / - 4.6 [83% CI: 3.1 / -3.8]	$p =$ 0.22	
Speakers aged 46 to 65			$p = 0.10$	$p = 0.16$		1.3	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / - 4.1 [83% CI: 0.6 / -3.5]	$p =$ 0.45	
Speakers aged 66 or more				$p = 0.83$		2.0	0	5	8.9 +1.1 / - 5.3 [83% CI: +0.9 / -4.4]	$p =$ 0.66	
	A.1					p=*	18 – 29	30 – 45	46 – 65	> 65	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	2.0	0	5	8.9 +1.1 / -5.3 [83% CI: +0.9 / -4.4]	$p = 0.95$			$p = 1.0$	$p = 0.83$	$p = 1.0$	
Speakers aged	2.0	0	5	8.9 +1.1 / -5.3 [83% CI:	$p = 0.95$			$p = 0.83$	$p = 1.0$		

30-45				[83% CI: +0.9 / -4.4]						
Speakers aged 46 to 65	1.3	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83% CI: 0.6 / -3.5]	$p = 0.84$					$p = 0.83$
Speakers aged 66 or more	2.0	0	5	8.9 +1.1 / -5.3 [83% CI: +0.9 / -4.4]	$p = 0.95$					
Ital. [Montella] <i>a</i> <i>bbacando</i>	0.4	0	23 (100 %)	9.7 +0.3 / -1.8 [83 % CI: +0.2/ -1.6]		0.5	0	23 (100 %)	9.7 +0.3 / -1.8 [83 % CI: +0.2/ -1.6]	
Male speakers	1.0	0	10 (100 %)	9.4 +0.6 / -3.5 [83 % CI: +0.5 / -3.0]	$p = 0.91$	1.0	0	10 (100 %)	9.4 +0.6 / -3.5 [83 % CI: +0.5 / -3.0]	$p = 1.0$
Female speakers	0.8	0	13 (100 %)	9.5 +0.5 / -2.9 [83 % CI: +0.4 / -2.5]	not sign. At all	0.8	0	13 (100 %)	9.5 +0.5 / -2.9 [83 % CI: +0.4 / -2.5]	not sign. At all
Younger speakers	1.0	0	10 (100 %)	9.4 +0.6 / -3.5 [83 % CI: +0.5 / -3.0]	$p = 0.91$	1.0	0	10 (100 %)	9.4 +0.6 / -3.5 [83 % CI: +0.5 / -3.0]	$p = 1.0$
Elder speakers	0.8	0	13 (100 %)	9.5 +0.5 / -2.9 [83 % CI: +0.4 / -2.5]	not sign. At all	0.8	0	13 (100 %)	9.5 +0.5 / -2.9 [83 % CI: +0.4 / -2.5]	not sign. At all
4 age-groups	A2	30-45	46-65	> 65				A.2		$p=*$
Speakers aged 18 to 29						2.0	0	5	8.9 +1.1 / -5.3 [83% CI: +0.9 / -4.4]	$p = 0.95$
Speakers aged 30-45		$p = 1.0$	$p = 0.83$	$p = 1.0$		2.0	0	5	8.9 +1.1 / -5.3 [83% CI: +0.9 / -4.4]	$p = 0.95$
Speakers aged 46 to 65			$p = 0.83$	$p = 1.0$		1.3	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83% CI: 0.6 / -3.5]	$p = 0.84$
Speakers aged 66 or more				$p = 0.83$		2.0	0	5	8.9 +1.1 / -5.3 [83% CI: +0.9 / -4.4]	$p = 0.95$
					A.1	$p=*$	18 – 29	30 – 45	46 – 65	> 65
Speakers aged 18 to 29	2.0	0	5	8.9 +1.1 / -5.3 [83% CI: +0.9 / -4.4]	$p = 0.95$			$p = 1.0$	$p = 0.83$	$p = 1.0$
Speakers aged 30-45	2.0	0	5	8.9 +1.1 / -5.3 [83% CI: +0.9 / -4.4]	$p = 0.95$				$p = 0.83$	$p = 1.0$
Speakers aged 46 to 65	1.3	0	8	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1 [83% CI: 0.6 / -3.5]	$p = 0.84$					$p = 0.83$
Speakers aged 66 or more	2.0	0	5	8.9 +1.1 / -5.3 [83% CI: +0.9 / -4.4]	$p = 0.95$					
Ital.	0.4	7	16	6.8		0.4	7	16	6.8	

[Montella] <i>a</i> <i>llieggiu</i>			(70 %)	+1.8 / -2.4 [83 % CI: +1.6 / -2.1]				(70 %)	+1.8 / -2.4 [83 % CI: +1.6 / -2.1]	
Male speakers	0.7	4 (41 %)	6	5.9 +2.9 / -3.5 [83 % CI: +2.5 / -3.0]	p = 0.37	0.7	4 (41 %)	6	5.9 +2.9 / - 3.5 [83 % CI: +2.5 / -3.0]	p = 0.37
Female speakers	1.0	3	11 (84 %)	7.6 +1.9 / -3.1 [83 % CI: +1.7 / -2.7]		Not sign.	1.0	3	11 (84 %)	
Younger speakers	1.0	6	4 (41 %)	4.1 +3.3 / -3.0 [83 % CI: +2.8 / -2.6]	p = 0.014 Sign.	1.0	6	4 (41 %)	4.1 +3.3 / - 3.0 [83 % CI: +2.8 / -2.6]	p = 0.014 Sign.
Elder speakers	0.8	1	12 (93 %)	8.8 +1.2 / -3.1 [83 % CI: +1.0 / -2.7]		cf. stand. test p = 0.018	0.8	1	12 (93 %)	
4 age-groups		A2	30-45	46-65	> 65				A.2	p=*
Speakers aged 18 to 29						2.0	3	2	4.2 +4.3 / - 3.8 [83% CI: 3.6 / -3.2]	p = 0.27
Speakers aged 30-45			p = 1.0	p = 0.08		2.0	3	2	4.2 +4.3 / - 3.8 [83% CI: 3.6 / -3.2]	p = 0.27
Speakers aged 46 to 65				p = 0.08		1.3	1	7	8.2 +1.8 / - 4.2 [83% CI: +1.5 / -3.6]	p = 0.27
Speakers aged 66 or more					p = 0.70	2.0	0	5	8.9 +1.1 / - 5.3 [83% CI: +0.9 / -4.4]	p = 0.14
				A.1	p=*	18 – 29	30 – 45	46 – 65	> 65	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	2.0	3	2	4.2 +4.3 / -3.8 [83% CI: 3.6 / -3.2]	p = 0.27			p = 1.0	p = 0.08	p = 0.04 Sign.
Speakers aged 30-45	2.0	3	2	4.2 +4.3 / -3.8 [83% CI: 3.6 / -3.2]	p = 0.27				p = 0.08	p = 0.04 Sign.
Speakers aged 46 to 65	1.3	1	7	8.2 +1.8 / -4.2 [83% CI: +1.5 / -3.6]	p = 0.27					p = 0.7
Speakers aged 66 or more	2.0	0	5	8.9 +1.1 / -5.3 [83% CI: +0.9 / -4.4]	p = 0.14					

Table 4: Analysis: A.1-2. The adverbials' recognition (A.1) and local recognition (A.2)

Question			A.3 Could you give an example?	Free answer.
A.3 Examples (raw data)	Age < 46/ > 45	Gen- der f/m	<i>Examples</i>	
Ital. [Montella] pe ccerto				
IT-CA-MON 11	26	m	<i>pe ccerto saccio ca quiro no stai bbuono.</i>	
IT-CA-MON 16	33	m	<i>quiro è ffessa pe ccerto; è stato isso pe ccerto.</i>	
IT-CA-MON 18	29	m	<i>te ro ddico pe ccerto.</i>	
IT-CA-MON 24	31	f	<i>vengo pe ccerto.</i>	
IT-CA-MON 25	28	f	<i>*aggio capito ca pe ccerto vengo; me lo mangio pe ccerto.</i>	
IT-CA-MON 4	75	m	<i>*pe' ccerto dio (giuramento); *certo dio?</i>	
IT-CA-MON 5	61	f	<i>*vao pe' ccerto.</i>	
IT-CA-MON 9	46	f	<i>ti vengo a trovà pe ccerto.</i>	
IT-CA-MON 13	62	f	<i>te ro ppozzo rice pe ccerto</i>	
IT-CA-MON 14	48	f	<i>Vengo pe ccerto.</i>	
IT-CA-MON 22	73	f	<i>lo saccio pe ccerto, l'aggio visto pe l'wocchi mia.</i>	
Ital. [Montella] a bbacando				
IT-CA-MON 6	38	f	<i>ragiona a bbacando.</i>	
IT-CA-MON 7	34	f	<i>si bbinuta a bbacando; ragiona a bbacando.</i>	
IT-CA-MON 10	25	m	<i>mende stia camminando pe ddindo a lo castagnito 12oncep pere so gghiuto a bbacando.</i>	
IT-CA-MON 16	33	m	<i>si gghiuto a bbacando.</i>	
IT-CA-MON 17	33	f	<i>*(si) ggira a bbacando (la vite); è gghiut a bbacando. / stao enno a bbacando.</i>	
IT-CA-MON 19	27	m	<i>*(si) ggira a bbacando (la vite); è gghiut a bbacando.</i>	
IT-CA-MON 24	31	f	<i>stao enno a bbacando.</i>	
IT-CA-MON 1	57	m	<i>aggio fatto no viaggio a bbaccando.</i>	
IT-CA-MON 12	74	m	<i>arriva a bbacando.</i>	
Ital. [Montella] a llieggio				
IT-CA-MON 18	29	m	<i>so gghiut a llieggio 'senza peso, tranquillo'</i>	
IT-CA-MON 4	75	m	<i>vai a llieggio.</i>	
IT-CA-MON 5	61	f	<i>si ghiut' a llieggio 'non soddisfatto'.</i>	
IT-CA-MON 22	73	f	<i>simo juti a llieggio.</i>	

Table 5: Analysis: A.3. Examples of the adverbials' usage

2.2. Variational features: How, when and by whom are prepositional adverbials used?

Question	B.1: Do you have the impression that this expression is frequent?					
	Possible answers: Very frequent – frequent – not frequent – do not know / not sure.					
B.1 Frequency	NS = not sure (reported to 1)	1. Not frequent (add NS)	7.5 Frequent	10. Very frequent	II.a Value (1-10) with uncertainties (95% CI) [+ 83% CI]	III. Significance of group- dependency
Categories exclusive Answers (raw data) in absolute numbers and % (1 line per item)						
Ital. [Montella] <i>pe ccerto</i>	2 (9%)	6 (26 %)	9 (39 %)	6 (26 %)	8.0 +0.8 / -1.0 [83% CI: +0.7 / -0.9]	
Younger speakers	2	0	4	4	8.7 +0.7 / -1.5 [83% CI: +0.6 / -1.3]	<i>p</i> = 0.12 not significant
Elder speakers	0	6	5	2	7.4 +1.2 / - 1.4 [83% CI: +1.1 / -1.2]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	0	0	2	3	9.4 +0.2 / -2.5 [83% CI +0.2 / -2.1]	
Speakers aged 30-45	0	0	2	1	9.3 +0.3 / -3.7 [83% CI +0.2 / -2.9]	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	0	3	3	2	7.9 +1.3 / -1.8 [83% CI +1.1 / -1.5]	
Speakers aged 66 or more	0	3	2	0	6.9 +2.2 / -2.1 [83% CI +1.8 / -1.7]	
Ital. [Montella] <i>a bbacando</i>	0	6 (26 %)	7 (30 %)	10 (43%)	8.5 +0.6 / -0.9 [83% CI: +0.5 / -0.8]	
Younger speakers	0	0	2	8	9.6 +0.2 / -1.3 [83% CI: +0.2 / -1.1]	<i>p</i> = 0.004 Significant cf. stand. test <i>p</i> = 0.003
Elder speakers	0	6	5	2	7.4 +1.2 / -1.4 [83% CI: +1.1 / -1.2]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	0	0	2	3	9.4 +0.2 / -2.5 [83% CI +0.2 / -2.1]	
Speakers aged 30-45	0	0	0	5	9.7 +0.2 / -2.7 [83% CI +0.2 / -2.3]	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	0	2	5	1	8.2 +1.0 / -1.6 [83% CI +0.8 / -1.4]	
Speakers aged 66 or more	0	4	0	1	6.5 +2.7 / -2.5 [83% CI +2.3 / -2.1]	
Ital. [Montella] <i>a llieggio</i>	0	13 (78.6 %)	3 (21.4 %)	0	5.0 +2.0 / -1.7 [83% CI: +1.7 / -1.5]	
Younger speakers	0	4	0	0	5.3 +4.2 / -2.8 [83% CI: +3.4 / -2.3]	<i>p</i> = 0.83 not significant
Elder speakers	0	9	3	0	5.7 +2.0 / - 1.8 [83% CI: +1.7 / -1.6]	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	0	2	0	0	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3 [83% CI +2.8 / -2.4]	
Speakers aged 30-45	0	2	0	0	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3 [83% CI +2.8 / -2.4]	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	0	4	3	0	6.9 +1.8 / -1.8 [83% CI +1.6 / -1.6]	
Speakers aged 66 or more	0	5	0	0	5.0 +4.1 / -2.6 [83% CI +3.4 / -2.2]	

Table 6: Analysis: B.1. The adverbials' perceptive frequency

Question	B.2: Who generally uses the expression? Free answer. [If there is no answer, the interviewer can help with suggestions, e.g., youngsters, the elderly, people from elsewhere...?]									
B.2.a WHO (age / social variation) on the basis of speaker judgment (raw data) <i>Groups of categories exclusive;</i> <i>Multiple answers in absolute numbers</i>	0. Not sure	1. Younger people	5.5 Everyone / No one in particular	10. Elderly people	II.a Age-attribution value with uncertainties (scale 1-10)	II.b Significance of group dependency	1. The less educated	10. The more educated	III.a Social attribution (see before) (scale 1-10)	III.b Significance of group dependency
Ital. [Montella] <i>pe ccerto</i>	2	0	8	13	6.5 +1.1 / -1.6 [83% CI: +1.0 / -1.4]		0	0	NA	
Male speakers	0	0	2	8	8.4 +0.9 / -2.5 [83% CI: +0.8 / -2.2]	$p = 0.27$	0	0	NA	NA
Female speakers	2	0	6	5	7.2 +1.0 / -1.8 [83% CI: +0.9 / -1.6]	Not sign.	0	0	NA	
Younger speakers	2	0	4	4	7.3 +1.1 / -2.4 [83% CI: +0.9 / -2.1]	$p = 0.46$	0	0	NA	NA
Elder speakers	0	0	4	9	8.1 +0.9 / -1.9 [83% CI: +0.7 / -1.6]	Not sign.	0	0	NA	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	0	0	3	2	6.9 +1.4 / -3.2 [83% CI: +1.1 / -2.6]	[d.f.: 2]	0	0	NA	NA
Speakers aged 30-45	0	0	1	2	7.5 +1.3 / -5.2 [83% CI: +1.0 / -4.1]		0	0	NA	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	0	0	3	5	7.7 +1.1 / -2.7 [83% CI: +0.9 / -2.3]		0	0	NA	
Speakers aged 66 or more	0	0	1	4	8.1 + 1.1 / -4.2 [83% CI: +0.9 / -3.5]		0	0	NA	
Ital. [Montella] <i>a bbacando</i>	0	0	10	13	7.8 +0.7 / -1.1 [83% CI: +0.6 / -1.0]		0	0	NA	
Male speakers	0	0	5	5	7.3 +1.0 / -2.1 [83% CI: +0.9 / -1.8]	$p = 0.62$	0	0	NA	NA
Female speakers	0	0	5	8	7.8 +0.9 / -1.8 [83% CI: +0.8 / -1.6]	Not sign.	0	0	NA	
Younger speakers	0	0	8	2	6.2 +1.2 / -1.6 [83% CI: +1.1 / -1.3]	$p = 0.01$ sign.	0	0	NA	NA
Elder speakers	0	0	2	11	8.7 +0.7 / -2.1 [83% CI: +0.6 / -1.8]	stand. test $p = 0.003$	0	0	NA	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	0	0	5	0	5.5 + 1.9 / -1.9 [83% CI: +1.6 / -1.6]		0	0	NA	NA
Speakers aged 30-45	0	0	3	2	6.9 +1.4 / -3.2 [83% CI: +1.1 / -2.6]		0	0	NA	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	0	0	1	7	8.6 +0.9 / -3.1 [83% CI: +0.7 / -2.7]		0	0	NA	
Speakers aged 66 or more	0	0	1	4	8.1 + 1.1 / -4.2 [83% CI: +0.9 / -3.5]		0	0	NA	
Ital. [Montella] <i>a llieggio</i>	0	0	1	13	9.1 +0.6 / -2.1 [83% CI: +0.5 / -1.8]		0	0	NA	
Male speakers	4	0	1	5	8.3 +1.0 / -3.8 [83% CI: +0.9 / -3.2]	$p = 0.95$	0	0	NA	NA
Female speakers	3	0	2	8	8.4 +0.9 / -2.5 [83% CI: +0.8 / -2.2]	Not sign. At all	0	0	NA	
Younger speakers	0	0	1	3	7.8 +1.2 / -4.7 [83% CI: +1.0 / -3.8]	$p = 0.40$	0	0	NA	

Elder speakers	0	0	0	10	9.2 +0.6 / -2.8 [83% CI: +0.5 / -2.4]	Not sign.	0	0	NA	NA
Speakers aged 18 to 29	0	0	1	1	7.1 +1.4 / -5.5 [83% CI: +1.1 / -4.1]	[d.f.: 1]	0	0	NA	
Speakers aged 30-45	0	0	0	2	7.9 +1.6 / -7.6 [83% CI: +1.2 / -5.7]	[d.f.: 1]	0	0	NA	NA
Speakers aged 46 to 65	0	0	0	5	8.7 +1.0 / -4.7 [83% CI: +0.8 / -3.9]		0	0	NA	
Speakers aged 66 or more	0	0	0	5	8.7 +1.0 / -4.7 [83% CI: +0.8 / -3.9]		0	0	NA	

Table 7: Analysis: B.2. The adverbials' perceived social/chronological variation: Who uses them?

Question	B.2: Who generally uses the expression? Free answer. [If there is no answer, the interviewer can help with suggestions, e.g., youngsters, the elderly, people from elsewhere...?]					
	B.2b WHO (social variation), on the basis of speaker judgment (raw data) Categories exclusive; Answers in absolute numbers	Not sure	1. Everyone / No one in	10. Other If applicable add category	III.a Value with uncertainties (scale 1-10)	III.b Significance of group dependency
Ital. [Montella] <i>pe ccerto</i>		2	8	NA	NA	
Relevant sub-cells		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Relevant sub-cells		NA	NA	NA	NA	
Ital. [Montella] <i>a bbacando</i>		0	10	NA	NA	
Relevant sub-cells		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Relevant sub-cells		NA	NA	NA	NA	
Ital. [Montella] <i>a llieggio</i>		0	1	NA	NA	
Relevant sub-cells		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Relevant sub-cells		NA	NA	NA	NA	

Table 8: Analysis: B.2. The adverbials' social variation: Who else uses them?

Question	B.3: When do people tend to use this expression (e.g., with friends, on TV, ...)? Free answer.					
B.3.a WHEN (situational) On the basis of speaker judgment <i>Categorised under 1 and 10 are exclusive;</i> <i>Answers in absolute numbers</i>	Not sure (reported to 5,5)	1. In Formal situations (e.g., in the news or with a superior)	5.5 No situation in particular / Both formal & informal types of situations / (add NS)	10. In informal situations (e.g., with friends or relatives)	III.a Value with uncertainties (scale 1-10)	III.b Significance of group dependency
Ital. [Montella] <i>pe ccerto</i>	2	0	21 [19]	0	5.5+0.6 / -0.6 [83% CI: +0.5 / -0.5]	
Younger speakers	2	0	8	0	5.5+1.4 / -1.4 [83% CI: +1.2 / -1.2]	<i>p</i> = 1.0
Elder speakers	0	0	11	0	5.5+1.1 / -1.1 [83% CI: +0.9 / -0.9]	Not sign. At all
Ital. [Montella] <i>a bbacando</i>	0	0	21	2 (at home)	5.8+0.8 / -0.7 [83% CI: +0.7 / -0.6]	
Younger speakers	0	0	10	0	5.5+1.1 / -1.1 [83% CI: +1.0 / -1.0]	<i>p</i> = 0.52
Elder speakers	0	0	11	2 (at home)	6.0+1.1 / -1.2 [83% CI: +0.9 / -1.0]	Not sign.
Ital. [Montella] <i>a llieggio</i>	0	0	14	0	5.5+0.9 / -0.9 [83% CI: +0.7 / -0.7]	
Younger speakers	0	0	4	0	5.5+2.2 / -2.2 [83% CI: +1.8 / -1.8]	<i>p</i> = 1.0
Elder speakers	0	0	10	0	5.5+1.1 / -1.1 [83% CI: +1.0 / -1.0]	Not sign. At all

Table 9: Analysis: B.3. The adverbials' situational variation: When are they used?

B.3.b WHEN (situational) on the basis of speaker judgment <i>Answers in absolute numbers</i>	1. No situation in particular / NS	10. Other E.g., in specific language domains / specialised language	III.a Values (scale 1-10) with uncertainties	III.b Significance of group dependency
<i>pe ccerto</i>	see 5.5 in the table above	NA	NA	
Relevant sub-cells	see 5.5 in the table above	NA	NA	NA
Relevant sub-cells	see 5.5 in the table above	NA	NA	NA
<i>a bbacando</i>	see 5.5 in the table above	NA	NA	
Relevant sub-cells	see 5.5 in the table above	NA	NA	NA
Relevant sub-cells	see 5.5 in the table above	NA	NA	NA
<i>a llieggio</i>	see 5.5 in the table above	NA	NA	
Relevant sub-cells	see 5.5 in the table above	NA	NA	NA
Relevant sub-cells	see 5.5 in the table above	NA	NA	NA

Table 10: Analysis: B.3b. The adverbials' situational variation: When else are they used?

Question	B.4: Does this expression seem more written or spoken to you?						
	Possible answers: written – spoken – both / not sure.						
B.4 HOW (code) On the basis of speaker judgment <i>Categories 1 and 10 are exclusive;</i> <i>Answers in absolute numbers</i>	No answer	NS (report to 5.5)	1. Written (of written 17conceptualisation)	5.5 Both (add NS)	10. Spoken (of oral 17conceptualisation)	II.a Average (scale 1-10) with uncertainties (95% CI) [+ 83% CI]	II.b Significance of group dependency (in brackets mere average)
Ital. [Montella] <i>pe ccerto</i>	2	0	0	7	14	8.2 +0.7 / -1.3 [83% CI: +0.6 / -1.1]	(8.5)
Younger speakers	2	0	0	6	2	6.4 +1.3 / -2.0 [83% CI: +1.1 / -1.7]	<i>p</i> = 0.005
Elder speakers	0	0	0	1	12	9.1 +0.6 / -2.2 [83% CI: +0.5 / -1.9]	Significant cf. stand. test <i>p</i> = 0.003
Ital. [Montella] <i>a bbacando</i>	0	0	0	8	15	8.1 +0.7 / -1.1 [83% CI: +0.6 / -1.0]	(8.4)
Younger speakers	0	0	0	7	3	6.6 +1.2 / -1.7 [83% CI: +1.0 / -1.5]	<i>p</i> = 0.004
Elder speakers	0	0	0	1	12	9.1 +0.6 / -1.1 [83% CI: +0.5 / -1.9]	Significant cf. stand. test <i>p</i> = 0.005
Ital. [Montella] <i>a llieggio</i>	0	0	0	0	14	9.4 +0.4 / -2.1 [83% CI: +0.4 / -1.8]	(10)
Female speakers	3	2	0	2	8	8.4 +0.9 / -2.5 [83% CI: +0.8 / -2.2]	<i>p</i> = 0.74
Male speakers	4	0	0	0	6	8.9 +0.8 / -4.2 [83% CI: +0.7 / -3.5]	Not significant
Younger speakers	0	0	0	0	4	8.5 +1.1 / -1.1 [83% CI: +0.9 / -4.5]	<i>p</i> = 0.30
Elder speakers	0	0	0	0	10	9.2 +0.6 / -1.1 [83% CI: +0.5 / -2.4]	Not significant

Table 11: Analysis: B.4. The adverbials' variation in terms of code: How are they used?

2.3. Do the adverbials present morphosyntactic prepositional variation?

Question	C. Have you heard of any forms that are similar to this expression? Free answer. [If applicable]: Have you already heard XXX? Possible answer: yes – no – not sure.			
C.1 Prepositional variation without semantic change Categories exclusive; Answers in absolute numbers and %	0. Speakers do not know morphosyntactic variation	10. Speakers mention they know morphosyntactic variation with the same meaning	II. Value (scale 0-10) with uncertainties	III. Significance of group dependency
Ital. [Montella] <i>pe ccerto</i>	10 (43 %)	Re certo mentioned by 13 speakers (57 %)	5.6 +2.1 / -2.3 [83% CI: +1.8 / -2.0]	
Younger speakers	4 (40 %)	6 (60 %)	5.9 +2.9 / - 3.5 [83% CI: +2.5 / -3.0]	<i>p</i> = 0.92 Not significant
Elder speakers	5 (46.1 %)	7 (53,9 %)	5.7 +2.7 / - 3.2 [83% CI: +2.4 / -2.8]	
Ital. [Montella] <i>a bbacando</i>	23 (100 %)	0	0.3 +1.2 / -0.3 [83% CI: +1.0 / -0.2]	
Younger speakers	10 (100 %)	0	0.6 +2.5 / -0.6 [83% CI: +2.1 / -0.5]	<i>p</i> = 0.92 Not significant
Elder speakers	13 (100 %)	0	0.5 +2.0 / -0.5 [83% CI: +1.7 / -0.4]	
Ital. [Montella] <i>a llieggio</i>	23 (100 %)	0	0.3 +1.2 / -0.3 [83% CI: +1.0 / -0.2]	
Younger speakers	10 (100 %)	0	0.6 +2.5 / -0.6 [83% CI: +2.1 / -0.5]	<i>p</i> = 0.92 Not significant
Elder speakers	13 (100 %)	0	0.5 +2.0 / -0.5 [83% CI: +1.7 / -0.4]	

Table 12: Analysis: C.1. The adverbials' morphosyntactic (prepositional) variation without semantic change

Question	C. Have you heard of any forms that are similar to this expression? Free answer. [If applicable]: Have you already heard XXX? Possible answer: yes – no – not sure.			
C.2 Prepositional variation with semantic change <i>Categories exclusive; Answers in absolute numbers and %</i>	0. Speakers do not know morphosyntactic variation	10. Speakers mention they know morphosyntactic variation with other meanings	II. Value (scale 0-10) with uncertainties	III. Significance of group dependency
Ital. [Montella] <i>pe ccerto</i>	23 (100%)	0	0.3 +1.2 / -0.3 [83% CI: +1.0 / -0.2]	
Younger speakers	10 (100%)	0	0.6 +2.5 / -0.6 [83% CI: +2.1 / -0.5]	<i>p</i> = 0.92 Not sign. At all
Elder speakers	13 (100%)	0	0.5 +2.0 / -0.5 [83% CI: +1.7 / -0.4]	
Ital. [Montella] <i>a bbacando</i>	22 (95,7 %)	1 (10 %): <i>re vacando</i>	0.7 +1.5 / -0.7 [83% CI: +1.3 / -0.6]	
Younger speakers	9 (95,7 %)	1 (10 %): <i>re vacando</i>	1.5 +3.0 / -1.5 [83% CI: +2.5 / -1.2]	<i>p</i> = 0.43 Not sign.
Elder speakers	13 (100 %)	0	0.5 +2.0 / -0.5 [83% CI: +1.7 / -0.4]	
Ital. [Montella] <i>a llioggio</i>	2 (0.7 %)	21 (91,3 %): <i>a llioggio a llioggio; lioggio; lioggio lioggio; a la leggera; (a la) leggja leggja; leggiu leggiu; a la leggja; re lioggio</i>	8.9 +1.0 / -2.1 [83% CI: +0.9 / -1.9]	
Younger speakers	1 (10 %)	9 (90 %): <i>a llioggio a llioggio; lioggio; lioggio lioggio; a la leggera; (a la) leggja leggja; leggiu leggiu; a la leggja</i>	8.5 +1.5 / -3.7 [83% CI: +1.2 / -3.2]	<i>p</i> = 0.86 Not sig.
Elder speakers	1 (7,7 %)	12 (92,3 %): <i>a llioggio a llioggio; lioggio; lioggio lioggio; a la leggera; (a la) leggja leggja; leggiu leggiu; a la leggja; re lioggio</i>	8.8 +1.2 / -3.1 [83% CI: +1.0 / -2.7]	

Table 13: Analysis: C.2. The adverbials' morphosyntactic (prepositional) variation with semantic change

2.4. Combined data – vitality

A-B.1 Vitality		Recognition (A.1): form 'known'	Local recognition (A.2)	Perceptive frequency (B.1)	II. Vitality		III. Significance of group-dependency (probability with Student's-t-test)		
Categories non-exclusive Answers in median values					Median value (scale 0-10) with combined uncertainties	[degree of freedom 29 unless explicit notice]			
Weighting / combination		double-weighted	simple-weighted	simple-weighted	(2x A.1 + 1x A.2 + 1x B.1) : 5				
Ital. [Montella] <i>pe ccerto</i>		9.7 +0.3 / -1.8	8.9 +1.0 / -2.1	8.0 +0.8 / -1.0	8.8 +0.5 / -1.0 [83% CI: +0.4 / -0.8]				
Younger speakers		9.4 +0.6 / -3.5	7.6 +2.1 / -3.7	8.7 +0.7 / -1.5	8.3 +0.8 / -1.8 [83% CI: +0.7 / -1.6]	<i>p</i> = 0.81			
Elder speakers		9.5 +0.5 / -2.9	9.5 +0.5 / -2.9	7.4 +1.2 / -1.4	8.5 +0.6 / -1.5 [83% CI: +0.5 / -1.3]	Not sign.			
4 age-groups		III <i>p</i> =*				18-29	30-45	46-65	>65
Speakers aged 18 to 29	<i>p</i> = 0.79	8.9 +1.1 / -5.3	8.9 +1.1 / -5.3	9.4 +0.2 / -2.5	8.2 +1.0 / -2.8 [83% CI: +0.4 / -1.0]		<i>p</i> = 0.61	<i>p</i> = 0.93	<i>p</i> = 0.71
Speakers aged 30-45	<i>p</i> = 0.70	8.9 +1.1 / -5.3	5.8 +3.7 / -4.6	9.3 +0.3 / -3.7	7.5 +1.3 / -2.8 [83% CI: +0.4 / -1.0]		<i>p</i> = 0.52	<i>p</i> = 0.89	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	<i>p</i> = 0.66	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	7.9 +1.3 / -1.8	8.3 +0.8 / -2.1 [83% CI: +0.7 / -1.9]				<i>p</i> = 0.62
Speakers aged 66 or more	<i>p</i> = 0.83	8.9 +1.1 / -5.3	8.9 +1.1 / -5.3	6.9 +2.2 / -2.1	7.7 +1.1 / -2.8 [83% CI: +1.0 / -2.4]				
Ital. [Montella] <i>a bbacando</i>		9.7 +0.3 / -1.8	9.7 +0.3 / -1.8	8.5 +0.6 / -0.9	9.1 +0.4 / -0.9 [83% CI: +0.3 / -0.8]				
Younger speakers		9.4 +0.6 / -3.5	9.4 +0.6 / -3.5	9.6 +0.2 / -1.3	8.9 +0.6 / -1.8 [83% CI: +0.5 / -1.6]	<i>p</i> = 0.61			
Elder speakers		9.5 +0.5 / -2.9	9.5 +0.5 / -2.9	7.4 +1.2 / -1.4	8.5 +0.6 / -1.5 [83% CI: +0.5 / -1.3]	Not sign.			
4 age-groups		III <i>p</i> =*				18-29	30-45	46-65	>65
Speakers aged 18 to 29	<i>p</i> = 0.92	8.9 +1.1 / -5.3	8.9 +1.1 / -5.3	9.4 +0.2 / -2.5	8.2 +1.0 / -2.8 [83% CI: +0.9 / -2.4]		<i>p</i> = 1.00	<i>p</i> = 0.86	<i>p</i> = 0.66
Speakers aged 30-45	<i>p</i> = 0.92	8.9 +1.1 / -5.3	8.9 +1.1 / -5.3	9.7 +0.2 / -2.7	8.2 +1.0 / -2.8 [83% CI: +0.9 / -2.4]		<i>p</i> = 0.86	<i>p</i> = 0.66	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	<i>p</i> = 0.72	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	9.3 +0.7 / -4.1	8.2 +1.0 / -1.6	8.4 +0.8 / -2.1 [83% CI: +0.7 / -1.9]				<i>p</i> = 0.51
Speakers aged 66 or more	<i>p</i> = 0.65	8.9 +1.1 / -5.3	8.9 +1.1 / -5.3	6.5 +2.7 / -2.5	7.6 +1.2 / -2.8 [83% CI: +1.1 / -2.4]				
Ital. [Montella] <i>a llieggio</i>		6.8 +1.8 / -2.4	6.8 +1.8 / -2.4	5.0 +2.0 / -1.7	6.2 +1.3 / -1.4 [83% CI: +1.1 / -1.2] [degree of freedom 29]				
Younger speakers		4.1 +3.3 / -3.0	4.1 +3.3 / -3.0	5.3 +4.2 / -2.8	4.4 +2.1 / -1.9 [83% CI: +1.8 / -1.7] [degree of freedom 29]	<i>p</i> = 0.009			

Elder speakers		8.8 +1.2 / -3.1	8.8 +1.2 / -3.1	5.7 +2.0 / -1.8	7.6 +1.0 / -1.7 [83% CI: +0.9 / -1.5] [degree of freedom 29]	Significant				
4 age-groups	III p=*					18-29	30-45	46-65	>65	
Speakers aged 18 to 29	p = 0.31	4.2 +4.3 / -3.8	4.2 +4.3 / -3.8	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3	4.7 +2.6 / -2.4 [83% CI: +2.2 / -2.1]		p = 1.00	p = 0.07	p = 0.09	
Speakers aged 30-45	p = 0.31	4.2 +4.3 / -3.8	4.2 +4.3 / -3.8	6.2 +3.8 / -3.3	4.7 +2.6 / -2.4 [83% CI: +2.2 / -2.1]			p = 0.07	p = 0.09	
Speakers aged 46 to 65	p = 0.18	8.2 +1.8 / -4.2	8.2 +1.8 / -4.2	6.9 +1.8 / -1.8	7.5 +1.3 / -2.3 [83% CI: +1.1 / -2.0]				p = 0.94	
Speakers aged 66 or more	p = 0.26	8.9 +1.1 / -5.3	8.9 +1.1 / -5.3	5.0 +4.1 / -2.6	7.4 +1.4 / -2.7 [83% CI: +1.2 / -2.4]					

Table 14: Combined analysis: The adverbials' vitality (A.1, A.2, B.1)

2.5. Significance of differences between all three test items

Questions	A.1 Have you already heard this expression? Possible answers: Yes – No – Not sure.					A.2 ... here in the area? Possible answers: Yes – No – Not sure.				
	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.1	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2	A.2
A.1-A.2 Recognition										
<i>Categories exclusive</i> <i>Answers in absolute numbers and %</i>	Threshold for unknown	0. No / Not sure	10. Yes	I.a Value with uncertainties on a scale of 0 to 10	I.a Significance (p)**	Threshold for unknown	0. No / Not sure	10. Yes	II.a Value with uncertainties (scale 0-10)	II.b Significance (p)**
Item 5 <i>pe ccerto</i>	0.4	0	23 (100 %)	9.7 +0.3 / -1.8 [83 % CI: +0.2/ -1.6]	vs 27 p=1.0 t-test p=1.0	0.4	2	21 (91 %)	8.9 +1.0 / -2.1 [83 % CI: +0.9 / -1.9]	vs 27 p=0.48 t-test p=0.39
Item 27 <i>a bbacando</i>	0.4	0	23 (100 %)	9.7 +0.3 / -1.8 [83 % CI: +0.2/ -1.6]	vs 13 p=0.009 t-test p=0.015	0.5	0	23 (100 %)	9.7 +0.3 / -1.8 [83 % CI: +0.2/ -1.6]	vs 13 p=0.009 t-test p=0.015
Item 13 <i>a llieggio</i>	0.4	7	16 (70 %)	6.8 +1.8 / -2.4 [83 % CI: +1.6 / -2.1]	vs 5 p=0.009 t-test p= 0.015	0.4	7	16 (70 %)	6.8 +1.8 / -2.4 [83 % CI: +1.6 / -2.1]	vs 5 p=0.009 t-test p= 0.015
B.1 Frequency										
<i>Categories exclusive</i> <i>Answers (raw data) in absolute numbers and % (1 line per item)</i>			NS = not sure (reported to 1)	1. Not frequent (add NS)	7.5 Frequent	10. Very frequent	II.a Value (1-10) with uncertainties (95% CI) [+ 83% CI]	III. Significance of group-dependency **		
Item 5 <i>pe ccerto</i>			2 (9%)	6 (26 %)	9 (39 %)	6 (26 %)	8.0 +0.8 / -1.0 [83% CI: +0.7 / -0.9]	vs 27 p=0.51 t-test: p=0.39		
Item 27 <i>a bbacando</i>			0	6 (26 %)	7 (30 %)	10 (43%)	8.5 +0.6 / -0.9 [83% CI: +0.5 / -0.8]	vs 13 p=0.000 high t-test: p=0.001 very sign.; Freemann p=0.003		

Item 13 <i>a llieggio</i>	0	13 (78.6 %)	3 (21.4 %)	0	5.0 +2.0 / -1.7 [83% CI: +1.7 / -1.5]	vs 5 $p=0.010$ t-test: $p=0.005$	
B.2 WHO (age / social variation) on the basis of speaker judgment (raw data) <i>Groups of categories exclusive;</i> <i>Multiple answers in absolute numbers</i>	0. Not sure	1. Younger people	5.5 Everyone / No one in particular	10. Elderly people	II.a Age-attribution value with uncertainties (scale 1-10)	II.b Significance of group dependency (Freeman)	III.b Significance of group dependency (t-test)
Item 5 <i>pe ccerto</i>	2	0	8	13	6.5 +1.1 / -1.6 [83% CI: +1.0 / -1.4]	vs 27 $p=0.77$	vs 27 $p=0.11$ t-test: $p=0.11$
Item 27 <i>a bbacando</i>	0	0	10	13	7.8 +0.7 / -1.1 [83% CI: +0.6 / -1.0]	vs 5 $p=0.06$	vs 13 $p=0.11$ t-test: $p=0.11$
Item 13 <i>a llieggio</i>	0	0	1	13	9.1 +0.6 / -2.1 [83% CI: +0.5 / -1.8]	vs 5 $p=0.06$	vs 5 $p=0.06$ t-test: $p=0.007$ Sign.
B.3.a WHEN (situational) On the basis of speaker judgment <i>Categorised under 1 and 10 are exclusive;</i> <i>Answers in absolute numbers</i>	Not sure	1. In Formal situations (e.g., in the news or with a superior)	5.5 No situation in particular / Both formal & informal types of situations / (add NS)	10. In informal situations (e.g., with friends or relatives)	III.a Value with uncertainties (scale 1-10)	III.b Significance of group dependency	
Item 5 <i>pe ccerto</i>	2	0	21 [19]	0	5.5 +0.6 / -0.6 [83% CI: +0.5 / -0.5] (proportion: 5.5)	vs 27 $p=0.49$ t-test: $p=0.53$	
Item 27 <i>a bbacando</i>	0	0	21	2 (at home)	5.8 +0.8 / -0.7 [83% CI: +0.7 / -0.6] (proportion: 5.9)	vs 13 $p=0.52$ t-test: $p=0.60$	
Item 13 <i>a llieggio</i>	0	0	14	0	5.5 +0.9 / -0.9 [83% CI: +0.7 / -0.7] (proportion: 5.5)	vs 5 $p=1.0$ t-test: $p=1.0$	
B.4 HOW (code) On the basis of speaker judgment <i>Categories 1 and 10 are exclusive;</i> <i>Answers in absolute numbers</i>	No answer	NS (report to 5.5)	1. Written (of written conceptualisation)	5.5 Both (add NS)	10. Spoken (of oral conceptualisation)	II.a Average (scale 1-10) with uncertainties (95% CI) [+ 83% CI]	II.b Significance of group dependency
Item 5 <i>pe ccerto</i>	2	0	0	7	14 (67%)	8.2 +0.7 / -1.3 [83% CI: +0.6 / -1.1] (proportion: 8.5)	vs 27 $p=1.0$ t-test: $p=0.88$
Item 27 <i>a bbacando</i>	0	0	0	8	15 (65%)	8.1 +0.7 / -1.1 [83% CI: +0.6 / -1.0] (proportion: 8.4)	vs 13 $p=0.01$ t-test: $p=0.09$
Item 13 <i>a llieggio</i>	0	0	0	0	14 (100%)	9.4 +0.4 / -2.1 [83% CI: +0.4 / -1.8] (proportion: 10)	vs 5 $p=0.03$ t-test: $p=0.13$

C.1 Prepositional variation without semantic change <i>Categories exclusive;</i> <i>Answers in absolute numbers and %</i>		0. Speakers do not know morphosyntactic variation	10. Speakers mention they know morphosyntactic variation with the same meaning	II. Value (scale 0-10) with uncertainties	III. Significance of group dependency
Item 5 <i>pe ccerto</i>		10 (43 %)	<i>Re certo</i> mentioned by 13 speakers (57 %)	5.6 +2.1 / -2.3 [83% CI: +1.8 / -2.0]	vs 27 $p=0.000$ t-test: id.
Item 27 <i>a bbacando</i>		23 (100 %)	0	0.3 +1.2 / -0.3 [83% CI: +1.0 / -0.2]	vs 13 $p=1.0$ t-test: $p=1.0$
Item 13 <i>a llieggio</i>		23 (100 %)	0	0.3 +1.2 / -0.3 [83% CI: +1.0 / -0.2]	vs 27 $p=0.000$ t-test: id.
C.2 Prepositional variation with semantic change <i>Categories exclusive;</i> <i>Answers in absolute numbers and %</i>		0. Speakers do not know morphosyntactic variation	10. Speakers mention they know morphosyntactic variation with other meanings	II. Value (scale 0-10) with uncertainties	III. Significance of group dependency
Item 5 <i>pe ccerto</i>		23 (100%)	0	0.3 +1.2 / -0.3 [83% CI: +1.0 / -0.2]	vs 27 $p=1.0$ t-test: $p=0.54$
Item 27 <i>a bbacando</i>		22 (95,7 %)	1 (10 %): <i>re vacando</i>	0.7 +1.5 / -0.7 [83% CI: +1.3 / -0.6]	vs 13 $p=1.48-10$ highly sign. t-test: $p=0.000$ highly sign.
Item 13 <i>a llieggio</i>		2 (0.7 %)	21 (91,3 %): <i>a llieggio a llieggio; eggio; lieggio lieggio; a la leggera; (a la) leggja; leggiu leggiu; a la leggja; re lieggio</i>	8.9 +1.0 / -2.1 [83% CI: +0.9 / -1.9]	vs 5 $p=7.29-11$ highly sign. t-test: $p=0.000$ highly sign.
A-B.1 Vitality <i>Categories non-exclusive</i> <i>Answers in median values</i>	Recognition (A.1): form 'known'	Local recognition (A.2)	Perceptive frequency (B.1)	II. Vitality Median value (scale 0-10) with combined uncertainties [degree of freedom 29 unless explicit notice]	III. Significance of group-dependency (probability with Student's-t-test)
Item 5 <i>pe ccerto</i>	9.7 +0.3 / -1.8	8.9 +1.0 / -2.1	8.0 +0.8 / -1.0	8.8 +0.5 / -1.0 [83% CI: +0.4 / -0.8]	vs 27 t-test: $p=0.54$
Item 27 <i>a bbacando</i>	9.7 +0.3 / -1.8	9.7 +0.3 / -1.8	8.5 +0.6 / -0.9	9.1 +0.4 / -0.9 [83% CI: +0.3 / -0.8]	vs 13 t-test: $p=0.000$ highly sign.
Item 13 <i>a llieggio</i>	6.8 +1.8 / -2.4	6.8 +1.8 / -2.4	5.0 +2.0 / -1.7	6.2 +1.3 / -1.4 [83% CI: +1.1 / -1.2] [degree of freedom 29]	vs 5 t-test: $p=0.001$ very sign.

Table 14: Significance of differences between items for all categories (from A.1 to Vitality)

** Significance according to Fisher-Freemman-Halton (first P-value) and the Student's t-test using Welch (second P-value).

3. Comparing data using exact values with uncertainties

The following tables compare exact means with uncertainties based on Roy’s calculator (2021-2022) for the Italian test items (items 5, 13 and 27). Age-cells – two age-cells (speakers aged 45 or less *versus* 46 or more) and four age-cells (speakers aged 18-29, 30-45, 46-65, 66 or more) are presented from left to right. For correlations with gender, only considered during the test phase, grey is used for answers from female informants, black for answers from male informants.

3.1. Recognition and local recognition

Graph 1: Recognition of Italian test forms (cf. question A.1)

Graph 1b: Recognition of Italian test forms correlated with age in terms of two age-cells (from left to right) (cf. question A.1)

Graph 1c: Recognition of Italian test forms correlated with age in terms of four age-cells (from left to right) (cf. question A.1)

Graph 1d: Recognition of Italian test forms correlated with gender (grey: female; black: male) (cf. question A.1)

Graph 2: Local recognition of Italian test forms (cf. question A.2)

Graph 2b: Local recognition of Italian test forms correlated with age in terms of two age-cells (from left to right) (cf. question A.2)

Graph 2c: Local recognition of Italian test forms correlated with age in terms of four age-cells (from left to right) (cf. question A.2)

Graph 2d: Local recognition of Italian test forms correlated with gender (grey: female; black: male) (cf. question A.2)

3.2. Perceived frequency

Graph 3: Perceptive frequency of Italian test forms (cf. question B.1): two significant differences between a lileggio and items 5 & 27

Graph 3b: Perceptive frequency of Italian test forms correlated with age in terms of two age-cells (from left to right) (cf. question B.1)

Graph 3c: Perceptive frequency of Italian test forms correlated with age in terms of four age-cells (cf. question B.1)

3.3. Other variational features: age-distribution, formality, degree of orality

Graph 4: Perceptive age-distribution of Italian test forms (cf. question B.2)

Graph 4b: Perceptive age-distribution of Italian test forms in terms of two age-cells (from left to right) (cf. question B.2)

Graph 5: Perceptive formality of Italian test forms (cf. question B.3)

Graph 5b: Perceptive formality of Italian test forms in terms of two age-cells (from left to right) (cf. question B.3)

Graph 6: Perceptive degree of orality of Italian test forms (cf. question B.4)

Graph 6b: Perceptive degree of orality of Italian test forms in terms of two age-cells (from left to right) (cf. question B.4)

3.4. Morphosyntactic prepositional variation

Graph 7: Morphosyntactic (prepositional) variation without semantic change (cf. question C.1): two significant differences between pe ccerto and items 13 & 27

Graph 7b: Morphosyntactic (prepositional) variation without semantic change in terms of two age-cells (from left to right) (cf. question C.1)

Graph 8: Morphosyntactic (prepositional) variation with semantic change (cf. question C.2): two significant differences between a llieggio and items 5 & 27

Graph 8b: Morphosyntactic (prepositional) variation with semantic change in terms of two age-cells (from left to right) (cf. question C.2)

3.5. Vitality

Graph 9: Vitality of Italian test forms: two significant differences between a llieggio and items 5 & 27

Graph 9b: Vitality of Italian test forms correlated with age in terms of two age-cells

Graph 9c: Vitality of Italian test forms correlated with age in terms of **four age-cells**

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